

THE IMPORTANCE OF WORD GAMES IN TEACHING LITERACY IN KINDERGARTEN

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Abstract. *The importance of speech development activities in preparing a child for school is incomparable. The educator must organize this activity in accordance with the requirements.*

When organizing creative activities, the teacher must pay special attention to solving problem issues, analyzing problem situations, as well as creating creative products of a pedagogical nature. The article provides information on the use of word games in teaching literacy in preschool educational organizations.

Keywords: *literacy, speech, language center, activity, exercise, thought, word game, interactive.*

ЗНАЧЕНИЕ СЛОВЕСНЫХ ИГР В ОБУЧЕНИИ ГРАМОТЕ В ДЕТСКОМ САДУ

Аннотация. *Значение речевой деятельности в подготовке ребенка к школе несравнимо. Воспитатель должен организовать эту деятельность в соответствии с требованиями. При организации творческой деятельности педагог должен уделять особое внимание решению проблемных вопросов, анализу проблемных ситуаций, а также созданию творческих продуктов педагогического характера. В статье приведены сведения об использовании словесных игр в обучении грамоте в дошкольных образовательных организациях.*

Ключевые слова: *грамотность, речь, языковой центр, деятельность, упражнение, мысль, словесная игра, интерактив.*

The future of independent Uzbekistan largely depends on a well-developed, intellectually capable generation and the quality of education and upbringing for it. Therefore, the upbringing of a creative person who loves the Motherland and the people, is loyal to the ideas of independence, and thinks independently is one of the priority areas of the state's educational policy. At the same time, ensuring the spiritual development of the individual through fundamental reforms in the education system is one of the urgent problems of this area, and the Law of the Republic of

Uzbekistan "On Education" states that a fundamental reform of the education system and the upbringing of a spiritually mature person are among the important tasks of state importance.

In his book "We Build Our Great Future Together with Our Brave and Noble People," the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, recognizes the idea that "a leader who is devoted to his people, capable of continuing the work we have begun, and who is fully developed in all respects, has the urgent task of raising the next generation as a complete person." Based on these words, it should be said that preschool education is generally considered the first stage of continuous education, which involves raising a child who is formed as a healthy and full-fledged person who is ready to study at school.

Preschool teachers develop literacy skills by continuously introducing children to oral and written language, building on prior knowledge and language experience. Pictures, games, and the printed word combine with oral language to help your child understand the symbolic imagery that underlies preschool reading and writing. It is advisable for his teacher to use a variety of interesting and engaging strategies in the classroom to develop preschool reading. It is very useful to make literacy a part of every day.

In the process of teaching literacy, various word games are played with children. In the process of word games, children are taught the qualities of memorization and the ability to save time as much as possible. Below are descriptions of several word games.

"FINISH THE WORD" GAME. The purpose of this game: To develop children's speech, enrich their worldview. Game process: The teacher tells the students an unfinished sentence. The children must complete the sentence in its entirety. For example, *a cat's baby ... (kitten)*. *A camel's baby ... (calf)*. *A horse's baby ... (mare)*.

"FIND THE RIGHT WORD" GAME The purpose of this game: To increase the vocabulary of students, to teach them to think logically. Game process: The teacher says one word in a sentence, and the children must replace it with the word they forgot. Different ... swam in the aquarium (fish). The bear loves ... (honey). Apples, bananas, oranges, these ... (fruits).

"WHAT DOES IT DO?" GAME. Purpose: To increase children's vocabulary. Game process: The teacher says a word to the children, and the children must tell what the animal or bird described in that word does. Cat (meows). Puppy (howls). Bird (flies). Cow (gives milk). Chicken (lays eggs).

The game creates joint, cooperative activities of children. Any game requires certain criteria, rules, order and discipline. In the process of the game, the child feels free, free, shows his true self.

He laughs, moves, expresses his opinion without shame or hesitation. During the game, he learns many social rules, learns discipline. The game plays a very important role in the life of a child. As adults need everyday life experiences, the game is just as necessary for a child. As the child behaves in the game, so he behaves in work later, when he grows up. Therefore, the importance of games in raising an active person is very great.

In conclusion, it can be said that the process of preparing for literacy in a preschool educational organization plays a very important role in the life of a child. During this period, he acquires knowledge about the environment, society and human labor. Through word games, the child understands the team, becomes conscious of the activity he is doing, and uses his voluntary attention during each activity.

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